

Semantic Technologies for Flexible Energy Grids: the Arnheems Buiten demonstrator

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HEDGE-IoT¹ is a large EU-funded project, which has the goal to support the digital energy transition by deploying IoT assets across different levels of infrastructure and infusing intelligence into the edge and cloud layers with the help of state-of-the-art AI/ML tools. One of the HEDGE-IoT pilots is *Arnheems Buiten*², a former testing facility from KEMA which operates its own local grid and is transitioning into an Electricity Campus. The aim of this pilot is the enhancement of energy flexibility by connecting energy assets and buildings in a semantically interoperable way using open standards, such as SAREF³. The first step in achieving the pilot's goal is to expose all information relevant to the energy usage behaviour of multiple buildings. This provides stakeholders with insight about the occurrences of peak loads of the various buildings, and when these are likely to co-occur, providing the opportunity to distribute loads differently in the future. Sensor data is made available in knowledge graph format, providing semantic interoperability by encoding data from connected sources using one ontology. By visualizing data in dashboards and similar interfaces, other relevant information can be included, like current energy prices and weather circumstances. To integrate heterogeneous information from multiple (types of) devices, we are developing and evaluating solutions based on semantic technologies. These solutions include 1) the Knowledge Engine⁴, which integrates heterogeneous information from various devices; 2) innovations towards machine learning on knowledge graphs for anomaly prediction and predictive maintenance, and 3) end-user visualizations of the data and predictions.

¹ <https://hedgeiot.eu/>
² <https://arnhemsbuiten.nl/>
³ <https://saref.etsi.org/>
⁴ <https://www.knowledge-engine.eu/>